

Writing process conceptions: A comparative study on disciplinary-socialized and disciplinary-naïve graduate students in two academic disciplines

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The current study aims to explore the differences in disciplinary-socialized (DS) and disciplinary-naïve (DN) students' writing process conceptions in the two distinct disciplines of humanities and natural sciences. A mixed-method research design was adopted. A writing process questionnaire and a verbal report were used for data collection. 80 graduate and postgraduate students from human sciences and natural sciences were sampled and asked to fill out the questionnaire. 20 of them were also interviewed to obtain their verbal reports. ANCOVA and VPA were conducted to analyze the quantitative and qualitative data respectively. Findings revealed a significant difference in writing process conceptions between students of humanities and natural sciences. It is concluded that DS and DN students differ greatly in terms of their writing conceptions.

Keywords: Academic Socialization; Academic Writing; Disciplinary-Naïve Writers; Disciplinary-Socialized Writers

1. Introduction

Academic socialization is a subject studied from different perspectives. Gardner and Mendoza (2010) have argued that academic socialization occurs when graduate students acquire the norms of their academic community, such as values, skills, and tacit knowledge. It has been claimed that academic socialization may lead to a myriad of positive educational outcomes including more positive academic self-views (Garg et al., 2007) and classroom engagement (de Bruyn et al., 2003). It consists of two stages: (1) 'anticipatory' socialization, and 'organizational' socialization.

According to the existing literature, the notion of 'academic socialization' and 'language socialization' are tied together (Poole, 1994); Language socialization theorizes that people not only socialize to learn/acquire a language but also

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use language to socialize and become full participants culturally (Ochs & Schieffelin, 2008). In this connection, Kulick and Schieffelin (2004) claimed that, through language and language application, individuals become socialized and competent members of their communities.

Arguing that academic disciplines are specific social 'communities', the current study also argues that academic discourse also deals with cases of language application in social interactions, albeit in academic settings (Duff, 2010), whose reflection is mainly observed in academic publications. As such, the skill to read and/or write research articles is essential for academic and professional advancement—i.e., for academic socialization. In this connection, Weidman and Stein (2003) have stipulated that academic socialization consists of six dimensions, one of which is participating in scholarly activities such as writing papers, contacting other scholars, and exchanging views on scholarly works. Hence, the current study considers graduate students who participate in scholarly activities of writing books or papers as successful and competent members of their respective communities of practice and calls them 'disciplinary-socialized' (DS) writers.

By the same token, those without academic publications are referred to as 'disciplinary-naïve' (DN) writers. The study argues that writing is a complex process consisting of a range of skills and tasks that play a part in academic socialization. Since writing is the basis of communication in academic contexts, it holds a higher position in comparison to other skills (Sparks et al., 2014). To examine the process of academic socialization through academic writing, the current study has sought to examine a variety of discipline-specific writing processes to observe how graduate students get academically socialized within a particular discipline through writing research articles.

The study is specifically interested in showing if there is any disparity in the way 'disciplinary-socialized' and 'disciplinary-naïve' writers perform in natural sciences (e.g., chemistry and physics) compared to human sciences (e.g., psychology and TEFL). The main objective of this study is to understand the conceptions of two groups of DS and DN graduate students about writing in light of the six factors proposed by Lonka et al. (2014). It also aims to examine whether there is any difference in writing conceptions between the students of natural and human sciences (i.e., NS versus HS). Laying the groundwork of research on academic socialization and in view of the literature, the following research questions are answered:

1. Is there any difference between DS and DN graduate students' writing process conceptions?
2. Is there any difference between NS and HS graduate students' writing process conceptions?

2. Background

2.1. Academic socialization

Process writing (see Sholeh & Talebinejad, 2022) as a classroom activity incorporates three stages externally imposed on students by the teacher, namely, responding (sharing), evaluating and post-writing. Kern (2000) discussed this text creation and interpretation as literacy. He highlighted the involvement of literacy with interpretation, collaboration, conventions, cultural knowledge, problem solving, reflection/self-reflection, and language use. Likewise, Knobel and Lankshear (2006) believed that literacies are generating, communicating, and exchanging meaningful content through the norms and specified texts within contexts as members of particular discourses.

Casanave and Li (2009) described graduate students' literacy practices as the ways they internalize the textual conventions of reading and writing, implicit procedures of participation, faculty-student interactions, and how this interaction and enculturation affect student and faculty identity. Academic literacy also engages students as skillful communicators whose communications are through conventional ways of communicating in a particular context (Berkenkotter & Huckin as cited in Newman et al., 2003). Lillis and Scott (2008) explained academic literacies in higher education as the problematization of writing and its pedagogy (cited in Coffin & Donahue, 2012). These literacies are practices that expedite learners' successful and full participation in educational discourse communities.

Mastering both the linguistic components (writing skills in English) of L2 and the writing conventions of their discourse community (academic writing skills) is vital for L2 learners. Moreover, these learners' struggling with linguistic problems and writing cultures of writers' native communities makes the language aspect complicated (Ventola, 1996). Ismail (2011) refers to the same intervention, discussing a group of students' academic writing at United Arab Emirates University. On the other hand, some other components such as discourse-community knowledge, procedural knowledge, genre knowledge, subject matter knowledge, and rhetorical knowledge are prerequisite to the knowledge of the discourse communities (Beaufort, 2007a; Salmani Nodoushan, 2023b).

Social positionings are built through academic writing (Hyland, 2002). In the case of students, this social positioning can be established by undertaking educational performance and productions. A good number of studies have addressed the elements that can enhance the level and quality of this interaction. Soltani (2018), for instance, discussed academic socialization as the production of social academic spaces. He focused on the educational achievements of an international student in different educational spaces at a

New Zealand University. The shifting active-passive pattern of his achievements highlighted the direct relationship among the communities of practitioners, the academic spaces associated with them, and the academic socialization of this student.

Some studies on academic socialization have focused on typical programs of education providing long term residency for students in academic spaces. Rourke (2012), for instance, considered the effect of doctoral nursing students' "limited-residency" on academic socialization. The findings indicated that "participation in scholarly activities" and "student-to-faculty" interaction in the case of these students are scarce while "student-to-student" interaction and conference-attending are encouraging.

2.2. Conceptions of academic writing

Academic writing can be considered both individually and socially. Disciplinary genres and their systems act like a stable framework within which academic writing evolves historically (Bazerman, 2004). Hyland (2004) has referred to social and cultural factors in a communicative text or any discursive form of communication whose norms are implicit as 'genre'. In fact, academicians' development in a particular discipline determines their learning of textual practices. Holland et al. (1998) discussed how doctoral students are "authoring themselves," cultivating their own academic voices. Similarly, Lonka et al. (2008) focused on students' personal epistemologies and expressions affecting their study practices in higher education.

In addition, increasing self-confidence and developing an awareness of the meaning of writing are some of the affective and social by-products of academic writing (Perpignan et al., 2007). Optimism and self-efficacy motivate students to see themselves as productive and active agents in the scholarly community (Pyhältö et al., 2012). Bandura (1977) suggested that task-specific self-efficacy strength and level can be altered through all kinds of psychological activities. A higher level of self-efficacy may prevent self-sabotaging behavior, such as procrastination. Writing is an important dimension in Schommer-Aikins' (1990 & 1993) questionnaire that assesses several epistemological dimensions. Believing that writing is an innate ability is in contrast with viewing writing as a creative and collaborative knowledge-transforming act.

2.3. Disciplinary differences

There has been considerable research on how disciplinary specialization determines students' epistemological beliefs, learning strategies, and products. This is considerably grounded in Becher's (1989, 1994) studies, based on former works by Biglan (1973) and Kolb (1981). To identify various learning styles, Kolb (1981) utilized the data from students while Biglan (1973)

analyzed academics' judgments about similarities in subject matters to establish hard-soft and pure-applied distinctions. Characteristically, there is an extent of internal accord over objectives, methods of investigation, and criteria of evaluation in hard and pure sciences. On the other hand, soft sciences such as humanities and social sciences consider knowledge as a kind of interpretation and lack internal unity (Helmenstine, 2019).

Additionally, there is evidence of disciplinary variations in areas such as learners' studying approaches (Entwistle & Tait, 1995), opinion about learning characters and knowledge types (Paulsen & Wells, 1998), vital skills for students and learners (Neumann et al., 2002), teaching preferences and methods (Neumann, 2001), and efforts particular to a distinct discipline (Breen & Lindsay, 2002). According to the researches, and comparing the students of hard sciences with the students of soft fields, the students of hard sciences are more likely to believe in absolute knowledge, and these beliefs probably emerge from the context of their disciplines (Paulsen & Wells, 1998; Schommer-Aikins et al., 2003). In another study by Neumann (2001), characteristics of distinct disciplines due to different teaching and learning dimensions were examined, and the findings demonstrated that soft disciplines emphasize critical thinking, oral and written expression along with analyzing and producing the content of the course while hard disciplines use limited amount of writing skill only for describing experimental findings and clarifying facts and figures.

In order for students to be socialized in their disciplinary communities, they have to follow the acknowledged literacy practices of their disciplines. The 'academic literacies' approach to student writing argues for the discourse multiplicity closely tied to the social practices of a community. As such, academic discourse appears to privilege certain groups of students over others. The situation is further aggravated when students come across diverse expectations in different courses (Lillis & Turner, 2001).

2.4. Discipline-specific academic writing

Clarence and McKenna (2017) argued that 'academic literacies' tend to bring together literacy practices with disciplinary knowledge structures, thus blurring the boundaries among the structures from which these practices emanate. Entwistle and Tait (1995) found that disciplines determine students' learning styles. For example, students of science and economics mostly reproduced facts through surface strategies. To the contrary, students of history and English were concerned with reproducing orientation and a 'serialist' (listing) style. North (2005) reported that in an Open University course about the history of science, students whose major was art achieved significantly higher grades than those who had a science background due to

differences in disciplinary culture and epistemology, so the results claim that disciplinary differences directly affect the students' writing. The results again beg the question: To what extent disciplinary contexts can transfer communication skills?

In a similar vein, Bozdoğan and Kasap (2019) highlighted the notions of discipline and genre in a sample study of engineering students participating in English writing courses. Their findings revealed that there is a "gap between what competences employers demand and what competences engineering graduates supply" (p. 59). The graduates represented no motivation and enthusiasm as language learners and writers. Some senior students explained the demotivation through the difficulty of terminology, lack of e-texts, e-exercises, and multimedia use in course curriculum. This underscored the notion of different learning styles in different disciplines.

Buzzi et al. (2012) addressed the idea of academic writing within discipline, with a focus on engineering, before interdisciplinary perspective in Learning Development (LD) as "work of a group of people who traditionally supported students through 1:1 and group sessions focused on academic literacies, of which writing is just one" (p. 485). This means that LD considers academic writing as a teaching material to be taught by writing experts and not the academic experts of a particular discipline.

Consistent with previous research is that of Zhu (2004) who distinguishes the same perspective among the academics of engineering and business faculties at an American university. In their explanation, these academics pointed to specific contexts within each discipline, different expectations, needs, roles and tasks undertaken by academics and students, and awareness of audience that renders academic writing as a learning goal along with 'learning to write'.

By the same token, the current study aims to examine whether there is any difference in writing conceptions between disciplinary-socialized and disciplinary-naïve students of natural and human sciences (i.e., NS versus HS).

3. Method

A mixed-method design that combines the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative approaches for an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (cf., Johnson et al., 2007) was utilized in the current study. The quantitative phase of the research, conducted by administering a questionnaire, was followed by verbal reports (VPA) representing the qualitative phase of the study. This research enjoyed an explanatory sequential mixed method. The explanatory sequential design had two phases. Initially, the investigators collected and analyzed quantitative data and, then, qualitative data were collected and analyzed to obtain explanations of the quantitative

results (cf., Creswell et al., 2011). The data in each phase were analyzed separately, and each data set led to its own inferences (cf., Ary et al., 2019). The present study was also non-experimental, which means that the researchers observed the phenomenon as it occurred naturally. The setting of the study was not controlled to embody a life-like situations. Such setting is suitable for studying inherent human characteristics (Mertens, 2019).

3.1. Participants

Through stratified random sampling 80 male and female participants ($N = 80$), including MA students, MA graduates and PhD students, were selected. The participants were drawn from two different disciplines, namely HS (English language and literature, and Psychology), and NS (Chemistry and Physics), comprising 40 students in each group. They were chosen from two Azad and three State universities in Iran to ensure the representativeness of the sample. Their age ranged from 24 to 37 years old, and their first language was Persian. Five sessions were held for data collection.

3.2. Instruments

To collect the data of the study, two instruments were utilized: (1) a writing process questionnaire, and (2) verbal protocol analysis.

The Writing Process Questionnaire consists of 25 items. The five-scale Likert-type questionnaire used in this study had initially been developed by Lonka (2003) in the higher education in general and had later been utilized by Lonka et al. (2014) to probe PhD students' conceptions of writing. It was validated by piloting the questionnaire to 41 PhD students. The questionnaire was also validated again by Cerrato-Lara, et al. (2017). The items of the questionnaire were subcategories of six factors underlying conceptions about the writing process: (1) blocks, (2) procrastination, (3) perfectionism, (4) innate ability, (5) knowledge transforming, and (6) productivity. Twelve items were assigned to procrastination, perfectionism, and productivity (each including four). Five items were related to the blocks while six and two items were assigned to knowledge transforming and innate ability respectively. Responses varied from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (fully agree).

In the current study, the content of the questionnaire was translated into Persian for non-English-major participants. The translated content was examined by an expert and found to be equivalent to its original version. However, in order to ensure the reliability and validity of the questionnaire in Iranian EFL contexts, it was piloted to 30 graduate and post graduate students prior to the main study. Then, Cronbach's α was estimated, rendering the reliability as .79, which is satisfactory. Furthermore, the questionnaire was

reviewed by two language teaching experts to examine its content and face validity.

To gain a deeper understanding of the phenomena and to uncover psychological processes that a person goes through to perform a task, Verbal Protocol Analysis (VPA) was applied (cf., Faerch & Kasper, 1987). The verbal reports administered in the current study were based on students' responses to the writing questionnaire and included both fixed and data driven questions (cf., Woodfield, 2010). In the verbalization process, Ericsson and Simon's (1984) fixed question helped formulate the four types of statements: (a) intentions, (b) cognitions, (c) planning, and (d) evaluations. These questions included; What did you notice about the situation? What were you paying attention to? Were you satisfied with your answer? In keeping with Jourdenais' (2001, p. 357) argument, the researchers asked "focused yet open-ended questions and provide[d] contextual cues," enabling the learner to reconstruct the situation. Moreover, to relieve the pressure on the participants, they were given the choices of either Persian or English as they felt relaxed to convey their thoughts. In line with Félix-Brasdefer (2008), observations have suggested that participants change the language of thought to their first language when having trouble with pragma-linguistic information (cf. Chinelo Obasi & Udofot, 2013; see also Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a, 2022). The DS participants were asked about their published written works in order to ensure the tangibility of their verbal reports and writing conceptions. Verbal descriptions of data were gathered to get a profound insight into the research query. To establish the validity of data, the content of the verbal report was reviewed by two TEFL experts.

3.3. Procedure

The present study was carried out in three distinct phases: (a) a pilot study, (b) a quantitative phase, and (c) a qualitative phase.

A pilot study was designed to scrutinize the questionnaire. Of prime importance was to determine the time required for its completion and identify its weaknesses to be eradicated in its final version. In the pilot study, 30 participants sharing the same characteristics with the main sample were selected. Based on the results of the piloting study, some of the items were modified and prepared for the ultimate aim of the study. In the quantitative phase, based on stratified random sampling, 80 male and female participants including MA students, MA graduates, and PhD candidates were selected from the two sample disciplines namely HS (English language and literature, and Psychology), and NS (Chemistry, and Physics).

Due to COVID-19 restrictions, the questionnaires were sent via email and social networks. The researchers kept track of the participants and resolved the

problems arising from ambiguity or complexity of the questions. Eventually, all of the returned questionnaires were gathered for further analysis both descriptively and inferentially. For the qualitative phase, 20 participants were invited to deliver their verbal reports and elaborate on their academic writing conceptions and its processes. Prior to this phase, the researchers obtained the participants' informed consent. The gathered data were then transcribed, analyzed, and coded.

4. Results

The data of the questionnaires were analyzed through ANCOVA. The items took a value from 1 to 5 and each belonged to one of the subcategories of the six factors, à la Lonka et al. (2014). Higher mean scores in each category indicated that the relevant factor was more dominant in the conception about writing process in an academican. Employing ANCOVA allowed the researchers to compare the mean scores of socialized and naïve students across the two different disciplines of NS and HS. For analyzing the qualitative data, thematic analysis was applied. As such, themes—i.e., summaries of information related to a particular topic or data domain—were the categories of analysis. Thematic analysis was performed based on Braun and Clark's (2006) six phases of thematic analysis to create established, meaningful patterns including familiarization with data, generating initial codes, searching for themes among codes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing final report.

4.1. Questionnaire results

The descriptive statistics of the questionnaire for the HS group were calculated and reported. The mean scores for the six factors were: blocks ($M = 2.28$), procrastination ($M = 2.39$), perfectionism ($M = 2.38$), innate ability ($M = 2.52$), knowledge transforming ($M = 2.49$), and productivity ($M = 2.19$). Those of the NS group were: blocks ($M = 2.87$), procrastination ($M = 2.98$), perfectionism ($M = 2.94$), innate ability ($M = 2.23$), knowledge transforming ($M = 2.05$), and productivity ($M = 2.65$).

Table 1
The ANCOVA Test Results for DS and DN

Source	Type III Σ Squares	<i>df</i>	M^2	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Partial Eta</i> ²
Group	1.58	1	1.58	1.043	.311	.018
Questionnaire	167.55	1	167.55	110.43	.000	.660
Error	86.48	77	1.51			
Total	1106.00	80				

a. $R^2 = .660$ (Adjusted $R^2 = .649$)

After checking the preliminary assumptions, the ANCOVA test was run in order to answer the first research question raised in this study. The main results of the test are presented in Table 1. This test indicates whether the two groups (DS and DN) are significantly different in terms of their conceptions of writing processes.

As reported in Table 1, a significant difference was found between the two groups on the scores obtained from the questionnaire [$F(1,77) = 110.43, p = .000 < .01$, partial $\eta^2 = .66$ representing a very large effect size]. It was, therefore, concluded that there were significant differences between the means of the DS and DN groups on the writing process questionnaire. The results indicated that the mean scores for the DS and DN groups were 2.095 and 5.439 respectively. This confirmed a significant difference between the two groups (Mean Difference = 3.344, $p = .000 < .01$, 95% CI [1.64, 2.54]). Compiling the results of the questionnaire, it was found that there was a significant difference between DS and DN graduate students in terms of their conceptions of writing processes. Accordingly, the first null hypothesis is rejected.

To examine the difference in conceptions about writing processes between the students of NS (Chemistry and Physics) and HS (TEFL and Psychology), another ANCOVA was run. ANCOVA results revealed that there is a statistically significant interaction at the .01 level between the two groups. Thus, there is a significant difference between the graduate students of NS and HS in terms of their writing process conceptions. The second null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

Table 2
ANCOVA Results for NS and HS

Source	SS	df	M^2	F
NS	1024.92	79	1024.92	5.75*
HS	2628.00	79	2628.00	14.75*
NS × HS.	664.45	79	664.45	3.73*
Error	5878.08	52	178.12	

Note: $R^2 = .51$; Adjusted $R^2 = .46$; $p < .01$; Observed Mean = 81; Adjusted Mean = Varies; SD = 2.715; N = 80

4.2. VPA results

Regarding the verbal reports, data obtained from the two groups of DS and DN were compared and analyzed.

Instances of DN group's verbal reports are presented below. One of the participants argues:

- (1) *"I have some ideas to start writing, but I don't know what I want to write to the end. I don't make a general plan in my mind. Pauses are allocated to thinking about ideas and sentence making."*

Another participant maintained:

- (2) *"At first some ideas come to my mind. It is difficult for me to have a general plan, but I like to have one. I do not know what I want to write to the end. I do not change my ideas. What I write is correspondent with my ideas till the middle of the text, then, I feel that the subject is a little detouring, and I stuck."*

Some examples of DS group's verbal reports are as follows.

One of the graduate students argued:

- (3) *"I am not completely ready, but there is one starter point in mind for writing. I want to draw a general outline and then start. I think completely about that and I have a general plan. I have a general plan but the details will emerge further. I write and find ideas together. I used to do this because I have done translations before. I am afraid of my text outline correctness but I don't stop writing to the end."*

Another participant of the DS group maintained:

- (4) *"I have an initial idea, but it is not complete. I should start to write. I have some short stops to find ideas. Most of my time is devoted to the formulation. I write about what comes to my mind. During writing, ideas came to my mind and I put them into the words. I mostly pay attention to forms of sentences in writing."*

The way the students in the two groups behave differently in terms of writing process highly affects their writing quality; the coherence of the text is strengthened when the ideas are emerging once and, then, formulated. In fact, repeated interruption by formulation while trying to generate ideas blocks out attention and reduces the text coherence. In this regard, Khaldieh (2000) claims that less skilled writers usually lack pragmatic and semantic constraints and are monodimensional. Victori (1999) also claims that advanced writers consider the text as discourse while the unskilled ones view it as a grammatically driven juxtaposition of sentences. It transpired that the two

groups differed in their formulations of writing. The DN group had difficulty in formulation. They mostly complained about the intricacy of the writing process and claimed it is time-consuming. The DS group, on the other hand, was found easily gliding through the formulation and less worried about the process. In fact, the DN group was relatively confused about the correct form of sentences during formulation, resulting in their spending extra time at this stage. They attempted to make their sentences in a way to seem native-like. They were even changing their ideas sometimes because of having difficulty in finding suitable English equivalents. This may stem from their level of proficiency, for they mostly claimed that they sometimes did not know the words and this resulted in changing their ideas.

In sum, the results showed a significant difference between DS and DN groups. According to the verbal reports gathered from the students in two groups, the DS group had a better writing performance in terms of overall planning, easy formulation, and concurrent revisions. These results were not far from expectations because the DS group had more experience in writing, demonstrated by their publications.

5. Discussion

As Zhang (2013) claims, writing is a difficult task since it is cognitively demanding. According to Lavelle and Guarino (2003), writers' beliefs, strategies, and multiple dimensions of the writing situation all contribute to this complex phenomenon. The current study sought to gather information about writing process conceptions of academicians. Having studied the relevant literature in this domain, it was concluded that using mixed methods (questionnaire and verbal report) has the 'affordance' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b) to show a great potential in evoking these conceptions.

According to VPA analysis, DN writers did planning together with their writing while DS writers did it mostly at the initial stage of their writing, making an outline prior to writing. As El-Aswad (2002) believes, planning can be divided into two main categories: local planning, and global planning. In local planning, writers plan their writing in a way that defines what to do next while in global planning, the writer makes an outline and a general framework of his writing and follows the planning. DN writers in the study were found to plan and write concurrently in the absence of any initial plan. As such, they were considered as local planners. On the contrary, DS writers, who fitted the criteria of El-Aswad's global planners, had a general view about the writing task prior to starting it.

Sasaki (2004) argues that students change their composing behavior from more local planning to global planning as they progress and become more proficient. This is consistent with the findings of the current research which

demonstrated that the DS writers behave as global planners and the DN ones as local planners. As de Larios et al. (2008) claim, highly proficient language learners, matching DS writers in this study, devote less time to formulation. Furthermore, Kobayashi and Rinnert (1992) claim that formulation equals translation from L1 to L2 for language learners with low proficiency. This was partly witnessed in DN writers. In fact, DN writers of this study were heavily obsessed with the accuracy of sentences during formulation, rendering this stage a time-consuming one. This may in part be rooted in their translating behavior (converting ideas into sentences) spotted during writing formulation. Whalen and Menard (1995) believe that translation damages and blocks generation of ideas. This claim also supports what was observed in the current study. In fact, most of the DN writers complained about the time-consuming feature of formulation and argued that they must devote a great deal of time to it. These two differences in the planning process of the two groups of writers, apparently, brought about differential outcomes in terms of their academic socialization.

Along with the previous findings, considering various characteristics of writers such as intentionality, genre awareness, competence and self-regulation, as linked to processes, is of a great importance (Zimmerman & Risemberg, 1997). For example, a writer facing a strange genre, may have some difficulties in understanding the pattern, and this causes the writer to merely work due to the rules in a piecemeal style. Thus, this could be one of the reasons why the DN group differed in their writing process conception from the DS group.

In addition, the results derived from quantitative data are entirely in line with what Ismail (2011) reported. The findings indicated that, regarding writing process conception, there are significant differences between HS and NS. It is worth mentioning that, according to Helmenstine and Anne Marie (2020), HSs are regarded as soft sciences and NSs as hard sciences. Thus, earlier findings related to other similar disciplines, in the case of being hard or soft, are applicable in this regard as well.

Given this, the findings of this study are compatible with what previous researchers have found. Silyn-Roberts (1998) claims that engineers have no interest in writing, and they think that their writing is not good. The roots of engineers' unwillingness to write can be traced into their preferred learning styles (i.e., active and visual) and the teaching style (i.e., passive and auditory) (Goldsmith & Willey, 2016). Also, according to Moore and Morton (2017), the majority of engineering graduates lack the level of writing skills expected by their employers. Beer and McMurrey (2019) believe that students of engineering, considered as a hard-science field, lack the writing skill because of the nature of their discipline which focuses on mathematical and practical work instead of written work. Furthermore, Ismail (2011) claimed that the

students of humanities are more positive about the ESL writing skill, which again is consistent with the findings of this study.

Along with advanced knowledge of the subject matter of a discipline, research has indicated that writing expertise involves knowledge of the discourse community of any particular discipline (Beaufort, 1999) as well as its rhetorical moves (Geisler, 1994; Haas, 1994), features of its genres (Artemeva, 2009), and the writing processes involved in accomplishing disciplinary tasks (Beaufort, 2007b; Flower & Hayes, 1981). Thus, ostensibly, knowledge of the writing process is vital in writing skill as long as DS group is regarded as being skilled at writing. It can be inferred that their knowledge of writing process is different from the DN group; this corroborates the findings of the current research. Furthermore, this difference in writing process conception across HS and NS as well as DS and DN writers may be due to the students' disciplinary culture. As Zhu (2004) mentioned, writing practice is restricted in engineering because of the quantitative nature of the discipline. Findings from the questionnaire and verbal reports complemented each other and showed that there were significant differences between DS and DN groups. In addition, differences between students of HS and NS were confirmed.

6. Conclusion

In this study, which is in a way an action research (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023a), writing process conceptions between DS and DN writers across two disciplines were investigated. The results indicated a significant difference in writing process conceptions between the groups of DS and DN students. Findings also highlighted the difference in conceptions across the two disciplines of HS and NS. A notable realization emerging from the collected data was that, compared to the NS students, HS students are more positive about writing skill. It was also found that DS students are active writers according to the different conceptions they have about writing compared to DN students. These differences may be due to the particular discipline's discourse community or students' disciplinary culture, or it may be because of various metacognitive and practical instructions students receive in their disciplinary curricula. Future work could follow a similar path with learners from different disciplines to identify the variations in writing process conceptions. Also, exploratory studies will bring to light the origins of such differences. It is hoped that the outcomes of this study will assist stakeholders to detect the variations of writing process conceptions within diverse disciplines. A 'washback' effect (Salmani Nodoushan, 2021c) of this study is to equip academics with the necessary knowledge to ensure that their students are capable of overcoming procrastination in writing.

Acknowledgments

We thank the anonymous IJLS reviewers for their insightful comments on the content of this paper and appreciate the editor's help and support. All probable errors of fact or analysis shall remain the sole responsibility of the authors themselves.

Authors' Statement

All of the co-authors of this paper confirm that they have discussed and conceived the article together. As far as the actual writing of the article is concerned, Elham Mohammadi came up with the initial conception of the topic and wrote the introduction section. Elham Mohammadi Achachelooei was involved in the literature review and the discussion section. Both of them supervised and edited the final draft. Masoud Allahverdi collected the data and prepared the results and an early version of the discussion.

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